

Pd(0) nanoparticle immobilized on cyclodextrin-nanosponge-decorated Fe₂O₃@SiO₂ core-shell hollow sphere: An efficient catalyst for C–C coupling reactions

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Abstract

Amine-functionalized core-shell Fe₂O₃ hollow spheres (h-Fe₂O₃@SiO₂single bondN) were decorated with Cl-functionalized cyclodextrin nanosponge, CDNS-Cl, covalently. The resulting hybrid system, h-Fe₂O₃@SiO₂single bondCDNS, was then used as a magnetically separable support for immobilization of Pd(0) nanoparticles, derived from a bio-based approach. The obtained catalyst, Pd@h-Fe₂O₃@SiO₂single bondCDNS, was characterized by using SEM/EDS, TEM, XRD, BET, ICP-AES, FTIR, TGA and VSM. Moreover, the catalytic activity of Pd@h-Fe₂O₃@SiO₂single bondCDNS was confirmed for ligand and copper-free Heck and Sonogashira coupling reactions in aqueous media. Comparison of the catalytic activity of the Pd@h-Fe₂O₃@SiO₂single bondCDNS and Pd@h-Fe₂O₃@SiO₂, established superior catalytic activity of former indicating the role of CDNS in catalysis. Furthermore, the catalytic activity and recyclability of Pd@h-Fe₂O₃@SiO₂single bondCDNS was higher than that of Pd@CDNS. The catalyst could be successfully recycled for several consecutive reaction times with slight loss of the catalytic activity. The ICP-AES analysis confirmed that the leaching of Pd nanoparticles was negligible upon each reaction cycle.

Keywords: Cyclodextrin nanosponge, Magnetic hollow sphere, Pd nanoparticles, Coupling reactions